

Arsenic in Rice and Rice Products

BfR Opinion No. 018/2015 of 24 June 2014

Arsenic occurs in various concentrations everywhere in the soil. It has been known for quite some time that cereals such as rice can contain more arsenic in the form of inorganic arsenic compounds (also known as inorganic arsenic) from the environment than other cereal types. The level of arsenic in rice depends on several factors, such as the concentration in the soil and in irrigation water, the type of rice and also the preparation of the food. If intake is long-term, inorganic arsenic compounds can impair various organs, even if ingested in comparatively small quantities. The intake of inorganic arsenic with drinking water correlates in epidemiological studies among other things with skin diseases and an increased risk of contracting certain types of cancer. For this reason, international panels classify inorganic arsenic as carcinogenic for humans. The carcinogenic mechanism of inorganic arsenic has not been fully clarified yet. Thus it has not been possible up to now to derive a safe intake quantity which may not involve an increased risk of cancer. The existence of inorganic arsenic in foods is therefore undesired in all quantities, although it cannot be completely avoided.

Examinations undertaken by the regional authorities responsible for monitoring have confirmed that rice and rice products such as rice cakes and creamed rice for infants can have relatively high levels of inorganic arsenic, which is of particular relevance from a toxicological point of view. These findings match up with those of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the authorities in other EU member states. On behalf of the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture, the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has assessed the health risk posed for various consumer groups through the intake of inorganic arsenic compounds with rice and rice products.

After making an assessment based on the Margin of Exposure concept¹, the BfR arrives at the conclusion that health impairments concerning the risk of cancer are possible. The levels of inorganic arsenic in foods should therefore be reduced to an unavoidable minimum (ALARA principle).

The BfR recommends that possibilities to reduce exposure to inorganic arsenic compounds from rice and rice products be examined. The data show that the levels in several of the rice products examined are higher than in grains of rice. The reasons for the higher levels of arsenic compounds in these rice products compared to grains of rice should be clarified. Options to minimise the levels of arsenic in these products should be evaluated. Furthermore, the consumption data on rice products should be updated so that exposure can be estimated realistically, especially where small children are concerned.

¹ The Margin of Exposure expresses the ratio between the exposure of the consumer and the exposure that causes a health impairment (e.g. an increase in tumour incidence) either in a test with animals or in epidemiological studies, which occurs additionally in a certain percentage of the exposed test animals or human population. It is used if no dose without effect can be established through experiments and it gives risk management indications regarding the degree of urgency with which measures are required.

		BfR Risk Profile: Arsenic in Rice and Rice Products (Opinion No 018/2015)			
A Affected group(s)	1. Children 2. General public				
B Likelihood of a health impairment	Practically excluded	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Assured
C Severity of the health impairment	No impairment	Slight impairment [reversible/irreversible]	Moderate impairment [reversible/irreversible]	Severe impairment irreversible	
D Reliability of available data	High: The most important data are available and consistent	Moderate: Several important data are missing or inconsistent		Low: Numerous important data are missing or inconsistent	
E Controllability by consumers	Control not necessary	Controllable through precautions	Controllable through avoidance	Not controllable	

Explanations

The purpose of the risk profile is to visualise the risk outlined in the BfR opinion and not to make risk comparisons. The risk profile should only be read in combination with the opinion.

B: The carcinogenic mechanism of inorganic arsenic has not been fully clarified yet. From the knowledge of the carcinogenic mechanism and epidemiological data known to date, no intake quantity can be derived which does not involve an increase in the risk of cancer. Exposure to inorganic arsenic is therefore evaluated in such a way that even the smallest quantities can increase the risk of contracting certain cancers and that the ALARA principle should be applied.

E: As consumers cannot recognise the levels of inorganic arsenic in rice or rice products, they cannot control them either. They can reduce their intake of arsenic through rice and rice products, however, by varying their consumption of cereal types and products (reduction of the rice percentage).

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/arsen-in-reis-und-reisprodukten.pdf>